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ISAAC CASAUBON AND MATTHEW PARIS

Isaac Casaubon is mainly known as a student of Greek literature and Holy Scripture.¹ Recently, Alastair Hamilton has presented some evidences of his studies on Arabic tongue.² However, we can affirm that he exercised his great abilities also on Medieval Latin authors: for instance, the 13th-century chronicler Matthew Paris.

When Casaubon moved to London, in 1610, he was directly protected by King James I. While in England, the scholar was requested to compose a response to the attacks against Protestant Churches that lay in Cesare Baronio's *Annales*. Casaubon's response was never completed, and the chapters he wrote were only published after his death as *De rebus sacris et ecclesiasticis exercitationes xvi ad Baronii Annales* (London, 1614).³ In this book, Casaubon was able to write a decisive page on the history of Paris' manuscripts.

During the XVIth century, in order to state that greed and rapacity were main features of Catholic bishops both in medieval and modern times, Protestant theologians had quoted several passages from Matthew Paris' chronicles, in which the avidity of the Roman Church was sharply described: Paris' *Historia Anglorum*, in fact, was first published by the Archbishop of Canterbury Matthew Parker, in 1571.⁴ On the other hand Cesare Baronio suggested that paragraphs adverse to the Roman Church could have been inserted by the modern editor: 'additamenta potius eius qui edidit novatoris, haeretici hominis, quum peculiare sit illis libros, quos potuerint, depravare'.⁵ Roberto Bellarmino did soon agree with his opinion.⁶

To contrast Catholic scholars on this point, Isaac Casaubon had to prove that at least one ancient manuscript bore the passages that Baronio had presented as modern forgeries. Actually, he did much more.

In the *Prolegomena* to his *Exercitationes*, he reported that many ancient manuscripts in English libraries, containing the works by Matthew Paris, attested also the doubtful paragraphs. Furthermore, he sketched some notes about a manuscript in the Royal Library, that in his opinion came from the very hand of the author:

1 M. Pattison, *Isaac Casaubon 1559-1614*, second edition (Oxford, 1892); H. Parenty, *Isaac Casaubon helléniste. Des studia humanitatis à la philologie* (Genève, 2009); A. Grafton, J. Weinberg, 'I have always loved the Holy Tongue'. *Isaac Casaubon, the Jews, and a forgotten chapter in Renaissance scholarship* (Harvard, 2011).

2 A. Hamilton, 'Isaac Casaubon the Arabist: Video longum esse iter', *Journal of the Warburg and Courtauld Institutes*, lxxii (2009), pp. 143-68; Id., 'The long apprenticeship. Casaubon and the Arabic', in Grafton, Weinberg, 'Isaac Casaubon, the Jews', pp. 293-306.

3 About the work see Pattison, *Isaac Casaubon*, pp. 322-41, and A. Grafton, 'Protestant versus Prophet: Isaac Casaubon on Hermes Trismegistus', *Journal of the Warburg and Courtauld Institutes*, xlvi (1983), pp. 78-93.

4 Mathei Paris monachi Albanensis Angli *Historia maior a Guilielmo Conquestore ad ultimum annum Henrici Tertii* (London, 1571; reprinted Zurich, 1589).

5 'Additions of the editor, a mystifier and heretic man, for those like him usually alter all the books they can touch': C. Baronio, *Annales*, x (Rome, 1602), p. 915.

6 R. Bellarmino, *De scriptoribus ecclesiasticis*, (Rome, 1613), pp. 205-6.

Coniectura Baronii, quae et a Bellarmino nuper est allata, vana, falsa, ridicula est. Extant in hoc regno vetera exemplaria eius scriptoris quae vanissimae vanitatis eam coniecturam arguant. Omnia enim illa habent, propter quae fides editoris hodie in dubium vocatur. Habeo ipse iam in meo musaeo codicem Matthaei, in membranis descriptum eleganter, e Regis Serenissimi bibliotheca promptum, eius vetustatis ut credatur ille ipse liber esse, qui ab auctore in bibliotheca S. Albani fuerat dedicatus. In eo codice nullam nos adhuc diversitatem observavimus quod ad illa attinet, quae de Papparum rapinis scribuntur.⁷

The manuscript, to which Casaubon refers, can only be the Royal 14 C vii, in which ‘Matthew’s gift [...] to St. Albans is recorded in his own hand on fol. 6v’:⁸ the Genevan scholar was apparently the first to understand that this book is an autograph by Matthew Paris.⁹

In addition, he gave a brief description of another manuscript seen in the famous library of Robert Cotton:

Extant etiam in bibliothecis Anglicanis alia eiusdem auctoris scripta nondum edita, ut *Historia minor* et *De vitis abbatum S. Albani*, in quibus similia, vel etiam graviora de rapacitate Romana lamentabiliter describuntur. Legi ipse nonnulla eius generis in vetusto libro, vitas abbatum illorum continente, quem mihi in sua libraria ostendit inter plurimos alios scriptos manu libros praestantissimos, eximiae vir probitatis et eruditionis Robertus Cotton Bruceus Baronettus. Non igitur illa sunt a Protestantibus Matthaei libris inserta, sed iustissimas illas querelas rei veritas extorsit ab homine alioquin, ut dicebamus, superstitiosissimo. Quare falsissima est Baronii et Bellarmini coniectura.¹⁰

The Cotton manuscript has to be Nero D i, which contains the lives of the abbots of

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- 7 ‘Baronio’s speculation, with which also Bellarmino agrees, is vain, wrong and ridiculous. In this Kingdom there are old manuscripts, containing the works by this author, and they show the vain futility of that speculation. In fact, these manuscripts have all the paragraphs under which Baronio doubted the editor’s good faith. I have at hand a Matthew Paris’ manuscript, that comes from the King’s Library, gracefully written on parchment: it is so old that you can believe it is the same book which the author inscribed to the library of St. Albans. In this book, I have not seen any difference from the edition, concerning the robberies perpetrated by Popes’: I. Casaubon, *De rebus sacris et ecclesiasticis exercitationes xvi ad Baronii Annales* (London, 1614), c. *****4v.
- 8 S. Lewis, *The Art of Matthew Paris in the Chronica Majora*, (Berkeley, Los Angeles, London, 1987), p. 457. See also: Matthaei Parisiensis monachi Sancti Albani *Historia Anglorum*, edited by Sir F. Madden, i (London 1866), p. xlv.
- 9 His statement was subsequently quoted by William Wats in a new edition of Paris’ work (London, 1640), cc. b5v-6r. Nevertheless, it seems to have been of no consequence for his editorial work: Madden, in *Historia Anglorum*, p. xlv-xlv: ‘Wats does not seem to have been aware that the Royal ms. 14 C vii was written by the hand of the author’.
- 10 ‘Other unpublished works by the same author lie in English libraries, for instance *Historia minor* and *De vitis abbatum S. Albani*. Here, the rapacity of Roman bishops is sadly described with similar words, and perhaps worse. I myself have read something like, in an old book on the lives of the abbots, that the excellent Robert Cotton Bruce Baronet, an accomplished and learned scholar, showed me in his library, among many other interesting manuscripts. Well, these facts have not been inserted by Protestants in Matthew’s books: truth itself caused this man, in other cases very superstitious, to cry. So, the speculation proposed by Baronio and Bellarmino is certainly wrong’: Casaubon, *De rebus sacris*, c. *****4v.

St. Albans.¹¹

So we have seen that a great scholar as Isaac Casaubon, widely known in the early modern times for his studies on Greek authors, was also capable of approaching a Medieval Latin manuscript in the most correct way; above all, he was able to draw from material evidence and textual details both a scholarly reading and a strong weapon in religious and political controversies.

11 *Catalogus librorum manuscriptorum bibliothecae Cottonianae, cui praemittuntur illustris viri d. Roberti Cottoni equitis aurati et baronetti vita et Bibliothecae Cottonianae historia et synopsis*, scriptore Thoma Smitho (Oxford, 1696), p. 56. Casaubon gave an account of his visit to Cotton's Library on 24 and 29 January 1614: 'adii d. Robertum Cotton, in cuius bibliotheca vidi thesauros antiquitatis admirandos. [...] Totum diem vel in literis scribendis, vel apud d. Cottonum nobilem Anglum posui. Deus coeptis benedicat. Amen' [I went to Mr. Robert Cotton. In his library I saw ancient and wonderful treasures... I spent all day in writing letters, or with the noble Englishman Mr. Cotton. God bless our undertakings. Amen]: *Ephemerides Isaaci Casauboni, cum praefatione et notis edente J. Russell* (Oxford, 1850), p. 1036.